

EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF NEURAL NETWORKS IN CLASSIFYING THE GENRE OF VIDEO STREAMS

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to consider modern video stream classification algorithms and select the optimal option suitable for application in video hosting applications. The study analyzed various neural network architectures, including ResNet18, architectures with skip-connections, as well as architectures with multiple parallel branches, on a specially prepared dataset containing video clips from films of various genres. The main attention was paid to finding a balance between accuracy and the dimensionality of processed data. The research results show that different neural network architectures demonstrate varying effectiveness depending on the size of input images and the specifics of genre classification tasks. The obtained data allow conclusions to be drawn about the potential application of deep learning in video content analysis and the selection of the most suitable methods for classifying film genres, which can contribute to improving the quality of video hosting services.

Keywords: video stream, genre classification, ResNet18, SkipConn Light, SkipConn Heavy, TwoBranch Light, TwoBranch Heavy.

INTRODUCTION

Video hosting is typically a web application through which users can upload and monetize entertaining or educational video content. The global video hosting market estimated at 8 billion dollars as of 2022. By 2030, a growth rate of 20% per year is forecasted [13].

The classification system of video content is an important component of any video hosting platform. In recent years, computer vision and machine learning have made significant progress, being applied in various fields [10]. Analysis and classification of video content is one of the interesting and challenging tasks [4, 5]. Genre classification based on video streams presents a complex problem due to the diversity of visual and audiovisual patterns associated with different genres. As well, the need to analyze and process large volumes of data in real-time.

The goal of this research is to find the optimal algorithm for video stream genre classification suitable for application in video hosting.

The research tasks include selecting multiple neural network architectures, collecting and annotating data, training, and evaluating key metrics of accuracy and performance of various video stream classification algorithms.

Frame-by-frame analysis of videos to determine the genre implies the ability to process information under time constraints [12] and high demands for classification accuracy.

RELATED WORKS

S. Jain et al designed a neural network based movie genres classifier in [6]. The characterization is based on low level audio-visual features: shot length, motion, color dominance and lighting key and the extracted audio features based on time domain, pitch, frequency domain, energy and MFCC. Movie classifier is designed using feed forward neural network, but convolution networks performs much better in image classification tasks.

Pradyumn P. et al [1] presents a model that is a combination of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). Custom deep learning network that can identify the type of video content and classify them into categories such as "Animation, Gaming, natural content, flat content, etc". However, there is no comparison to performance of pretrained models, common approach as transfer learning. They enhance the performance of the model novel keyframe extraction method they included to classify only the keyframes, thereby reducing the overall processing time without sacrificing any significant performance. But recurrent networks tends to potential slow inference.

DATA ANALYSIS

For training and testing the models, a specially prepared dataset, collected and manually labeled by us, is used. The dataset contains video clips from films of various genres and consists of 2613 annotated frames with dimensions of 256 x 128 pixels. The dataset is divided into training and testing sets, with each video clip accompanied by a label indicating its genre.

Fig.1 Distribution of the frames for each genre in the training set.

The histogram [Fig. 1] displays the number of samples for each film genre in the training set. From the graph, it can be observed that the genres (drama) and (thriller) have the highest number of samples in the dataset, indicating that these genres may be the most common or that more data was collected for these categories. On the other hand, the genres (fantasy) and (musical) have a relatively smaller number of samples. Such

a relatively unbalanced distribution of classes is important to consider in order to accurately evaluate the accuracy of the trained model.

It is important to note that the task of genre classification can also be transformed into a multi-class classification task, as in the modern world, many films are created at the boundaries of different genres, blending various approaches.

Fig. 2. Examples of frames from some classes. a – musical, b – animation, c – fantasy, d – adventure

METHOD

Due to the specificity of the task, the classification of film genres is performed frame by frame. This is because for recurrent neural networks capable of analyzing sequences of frames to consider context, there may not be enough time for processing in real-time conditions [12].

It is known that in the encoding process, redundant video data in a series of adjacent frames is eliminated. Keyframes (I-frames) are used to restore the other frames and are placed sequentially every 10-15 frames. From a computational point of view, classifying the video stream based on keyframes is the least costly [3].

Thus, the emphasis is placed on the speed and accuracy of classification for individual frames (fig. 2). For the research, the following neural network architectures were chosen:

1. **ResNet18** [2] as the baseline model. This architecture is used to compare the effectiveness and speed of more specialized models.

2. **SkipConn Light and SkipConn Heavy** [7] are convolutional neural networks, where the Light version has fewer layers compared to Heavy. Both architectures use skip connections to improve gradient flow and prevent the vanishing gradient problem, with the Heavy version differing from the Light one by having more convolutions inside the basic block and more basic blocks.

3. **TwoBranch Light and TwoBranch Heavy** [8] are architectures with two branches: one with regular convolution and the other with expanded convolution (broad convolution). The branches are merged at a certain processing stage for joint analysis of the obtained features.

Since the ultimate goal for the real-time processing of video fragments requires achieving maximum model performance with unchanged computational hardware characteristics, the influence of input image sizes on model accuracy was also tested, as reducing the dimensionality of processed objects can contribute to achieving the stated goal [9].

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed models, accuracy is used as the performance metric. The accuracy metric evaluates the proportion of correctly classified examples among the entire dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{Number\ of\ Correct\ Predictions}{Total\ Number\ of\ Predictions}$$

RESULTS

Each model was trained for 25 epochs using the CrossEntropyLoss loss function and the SGD optimizer [11]. Accuracy evaluation was conducted on a separate validation set comprising 20% of the main dataset.

Table 1 presents the results of the study - the validation accuracy for different neural network architectures at various input image sizes: 64x64, 128x128, and 256x256 pixels.

Table 1.

Evaluation of training accuracy for different models.

Size	ResNet18	SkipConn Light	SkipConn Heavy	TwoBranch Light	TwoBranch Heavy
64 x 64	0.516	0.376	0.389	0.268	0.354
128 x 128	0.544	0.387	0.356	0.290	0.327
256 x 256	0.573	0.376	0.389	0.243	0.391

DISCUSSION

From the data in the table, the following can be observed:

- ResNet18 demonstrates a consistent improvement in accuracy with increasing image size, starting from 0.516 (for 64x64) to 0.573 (for 256x256), indicating that this model best extracts information from larger images.

- SkipConn Light and SkipConn Heavy show similar results regardless of the input image size, with the SkipConn Heavy model not demonstrating significant improvement compared to the lighter version. This may

suggest that the additional complexity of the Heavy architecture does not yield the expected improvement for this task.

- TwoBranch Light generally exhibits lower accuracy compared to other models, which may indicate insufficient capability of the architecture to extract useful features from small and medium-sized images for this specific task.

- On the contrary, TwoBranch Heavy shows relatively high accuracy on larger images, reaching 0.391 for the size of 256x256, which is the best result among all custom models for this image size.

Fig. 3.

Histogram of classification accuracy for each class by the trained ResNet18 model with maximum input image.

The graph displays the accuracy of correct predictions for various film genres classified using the ResNet18 model with an input image size of 256x256. Based on the graph, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Action films demonstrate the lowest prediction accuracy, which may indicate that the characteristics of the action genre are more challenging to extract during frame-by-frame analysis or that they overlap with characteristics of other genres.

- Fantasy and animation genres show the highest level of accuracy among the studied genres, suggesting the presence of unique, easily recognizable visual elements specific to these genres.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents an approach to film genre classification based on frame-by-frame analysis of video streams. Various neural network architectures were investigated to determine the most effective ones for the task at hand. The obtained results allow conclusions to be drawn about the potential application of deep learning in video content analysis and the selection of optimal methods for film genre classification.

References

1. Pradyumn Patil, Vishwajeet Pawar, Yash Pawar and Shruti Pisal. «Video Content Classification using Deep Learning.» ArXiv, abs/2111.13813 (2021).
2. He, Kaiming & Zhang, Xiangyu & Ren, Shaoqing & Sun, Jian. (2016). Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. 770-778. 10.1109/CVPR.2016.90.
3. Ning Xu, Anan Liu, Yongkang Wong, Yongdong Zhang, Weizhi Nie, Yuting Su and M. Kankanhalli. "Dual-Stream Recurrent Neural Network for

Video Captioning." IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology, 29 (2019): 2482-2493.

4. Thomas Sobchack. "Genre Film: A Classical Experience." Literature-film Quarterly, 3 (1975): 196.

5. Laura U. Marks. "A Deleuzian politics of hybrid cinema." Screen, 35 (1994): 244-264.

6. S. Jain and R. S. Jadon. "Movies genres classifier using neural network." 2009 24th International Symposium on Computer and Information Sciences (2009): 575-580.

7. O. Oyedotun, Kassem Al Ismaeil and Djamila Aouada. "Training very deep neural networks: Rethinking the role of skip connections." Neurocomputing, 441 (2021): 105-117.

8. Jie Liu, Chuming Li, Feng Liang, Chen Lin, Ming Sun, Junjie Yan, Wanli Ouyang and Dong Xu. "Inception Convolution with Efficient Dilation Search." ArXiv (2021).

9. C. Sabottke and B. Spieler. "The Effect of Image Resolution on Deep Learning in Radiography." Radiology. Artificial intelligence, 21 (2020): e190015.

10. Kublik E.I., Labintsev A.I., Chipchagov M.S., Shilov M.A. Improving the Effectiveness of Radio Advertising Campaigns by Integrating Digital Monitoring Tools. Humanities and Social Sciences. Bulletin of the Financial University. 2023;13(5):121-128. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.26794/2226-7867-2023-13-5-121-128>

11. Tian, Yingjie, Yuqi Zhang, and Haibin Zhang. 2023. "Recent Advances in Stochastic Gradient Descent in Deep Learning" Mathematics 11, no. 3: 682.

12. Antonio Orvieto, Samuel L Smith, Albert Gu, Anushan Fernando, Caglar Gulcehre, Razvan Pascanu, Soham De. «Resurrecting Recurrent Neural Networks for Long Sequences» . ArXiv,

abs/2303.06349 (2023)

13. Online Video Platform Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Component, By Type (Video Processing, Video Analytics, Video Management), By Streaming Type, By End-user, By Region,

And Segment Forecasts, 2023 - 2030.
<https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/online-video-platforms-market>.